

Original Article

Classroom Assessment Techniques and their Impact on Students Performance at Primary Level

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Abstract

The main aim of this study was to determine the impact of formal and informal assessment techniques on the performance of primary level student. The assessment is used in everyday life to refer to different things, depending on the context, and the philosophy underlying the system in which it is used. A survey method was used. The mix method was used for this study and data was collected through instruments. The qualitative data were collected through questionnaire. Population of the study was student of science subject in primary level classes. The sample consisted of 69 students enrolled in grade 2 to 5 at primary school in Karachi. For this study, utilized pre-test and post-test and questionnaire for collection of information. Students in the treatment group outperformed their counterparts in the control group by a significant margin. Furthermore, while linked to control group, students' academic performance and performance in class can both be improved by using assessment as a teaching approach. According to the study's findings, the students appeared to have enjoyed their time there and were open to being evaluated. Students showed interest in learning assessment techniques in their classes.

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INTRODUCTION

Learning assessment is a continuous process rather than a one-time event. It involves the methodical and cautious process of evaluating, considering, and adjusting the learning strategies. Continuous assessment is when a teacher conducts ongoing or continuous evaluations in the classroom (Prouty & George, 2003). Periodically, observations are made during this process in order to gather information about the performance, comprehension, and knowledge levels of the students. Students are given specific assignments based on their prior performance in the classroom. The teacher assesses the students' performance in class by observing their actions. They can also use it to determine what the students have learned. According to Abejehu (2016), continuous assessment is an essential component of the teaching process and a crucial instrument in efforts to ensure the quality of education.

My interest in learning quality, a key global challenge today, is what motivates me to examine assessment systems and how they affect student performance. Depending on the situation and the system's guiding ideology, assessment can be used to refer to a variety of concepts in daily life. The following part presents its operational meaning in order to elicit how it is used in this thesis. There are various levels at which assessment can be employed as a component of the curriculum, including national, institutional, and student achievement at the course level. To promote student learning, teachers must possess advanced skills to measure and examine the learning progress of students and then resolve on the best course of action for both students and teachers (Brooks et al., 2021; Heitink, Van der Kleij, Veldkamp, Schildkamp, & Kippers, 2016). Furthermore, one of the more sophisticated teacher skills has been identified as enhancing student involvement in their own learning progress, which is a fundamental aspect of AFL (Christoforidou et al., 2014). According to Kippers, Wolterinck, Schildkamp, Poortman, and Visscher (2018), teachers present a wide range of proficiency in implementing AFL in the classroom, reflecting the

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complexity of the language. As a result, the potential advantages of AAL for students are frequently still unrealized (Kingston & Nash, 2011).

Research Objective

The determination of this study to measure the impact of assessment on primary student performance. Additionally, it would enable the instructor to enhance their methods and facilitate the learning process of their students. The process of assessment (when done well) will engage students in behaviors and activities that support them to learn what you want them to.

Research Questions

In order to guide the following research topics, the study integrated data gathering and analysis of mixed methods:

- Is there statically significance impact of assessment strategies on the performance of students used in daily class room?
- How do students think about different approaches to evaluation?
- How do teachers feel about assessments being utilized as a teaching tool to evaluate student performance?

Hypothesis

Is there astatically significant relation between impact of assessment strategies on the performance of student?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Standardized tests that employ questions with few possible answers are referred to as traditional assessments. True or false, multiple choice, and a few short answer questions are all included. In addition to the final response, some testing techniques—also referred to as performance-based assessment, alternative assessment, or authentic assessment—focus on the steps a student takes to arrive at their answer. Essay questions and lengthy responses are examples of alternative evaluation. At every level of self-regulated learning, students have access to a multitude of learning possibilities through the self-assessment process, which also makes learning more effective and goal-oriented (Yan & Boud, 2022). By identifying personal and environmental resources, self-assessment, for example, assists students in setting objectives and determining the best learning tactics. Additionally, it can be used to monitor learning progress, promote self-correction, and guide learning toward learning goals. Lastly, it can be applied to evaluate learning objectives and pinpoint areas that require further study (Harris & Brown, 2018; Yan, 2020).

A year later, Gipps (1994) coined the term "model shift" to describe the transition from psycho-metric to a more comprehensive educational evaluation as well as other modifications in assessment methods, acknowledging that learning and assessment had changed. As previous theories of Keeves (1994) and Broadfoot (1979), Eckstein (1996) believes that the implementation of written examinations as a selection mechanism was motivated by the modernization of schemes and the resulting improved rivalry for facilities, such as better jobs and higher education. The social selection process would be validated by such tests and the certification of the chosen applicants. The study referred to the classroom as the "black box," where "input" (students, teachers, resources, and parental concerns) is provided with the expectation that competent, knowledgeable pupils will produce superior results that will satisfy the instructors (Black & William, 1998b).

Black and Williams agreed that while thinking about better output, the "black box" is frequently overlooked. Some of the "inputs" into the "black box" may be squandered as a result. This research suggests that learning should take precedence over measurement. According to Brandfort et al. (1999b), a decent learning atmosphere must comprise three key components for students: learner centered, assessment centered and knowledge based. As based on knowledge, the pupils learn connecting the learner's strengths, interests, and preconceptions to their present academic and learning objectives is the main goal of learner-centered education. Assessment-centered learning environments give students numerous chances to track and demonstrate how well they are rewriting their ideas and applying what they have learned to new tasks and circumstances.

The process of collecting, analyzing, and using data to draw conclusions about pupils' academic performance is referred to as "assessment." This act of applying evidence to programs, processes, materials, or systems is referred to as "evaluation" (Harlen, 2007). There are various levels at which assessment can be employed as a component of the curriculum, including national, institutional, and student achievement at the course level. There is growing empirical support for the Education Sector Policy (Charman et al. 1995; Ramsden et al. 1986).

Instead of being taught as discrete, incomplete skills, teacher skills must be taught as part of an integrated approach in order to improve (Christoforidou & Kyriakides, 2021). According to research, teachers may be better prepared to develop complex abilities, such as those needed for AFL, and apply these skills to real-life situations when education concentrates on skill groupings rather than standalone skills (Creemers et al., 2013, Merrill, 2012). In the context of AFL, the competence-based approach is best understood as a continuum of educator competencies (Christoforidou & Kyriakides, 2021). The teachers must constantly address the fundamentals of the AFL approach before moving further, for instance, since they cannot begin creating assessment systems unless they have a firm grasp of the knowledge objectives and achievement standards for their pupils. As stated that Francom and Gardner (2014), "A learning experience must be oriented on learning tasks, which are based on real world problems or procedures that learners are expected to encounter in the real world". This brings the task-centered focus and the competence-based approach into alignment. The requirement that TPD programs integrate AFL with topic knowledge emphasizes the significance of real-life tasks (Desimone, 2009). Teachers will find it extremely difficult to comprehend how pupils think and much more difficult to modify their education as a result of this lack of content knowledge (Heitink, Van der Kleij, Veldkamp, Schildkamp & Kippers, 2016).

Students' performance is impacted by assessments in both positive and bad ways. According to Mayers (1986), it takes years for students' perceptions of evaluation to shift. Educationalists are increasingly putting a lot of focus on effective assessment strategies because students spend most of their time in the classroom, where teachers evaluate their learning and apply remedial measures during classes. Students that work in groups talk about the ideas with their classmates, who give them more information and improve their understanding of one another. Students are more driven to put in more effort when teachers assess their performance in groups because they are aware that they are all striving toward the same objective. According to Webb (1985), more explanations and cooperative engagement have a stronger impact on students' performance and reduce their anxiety levels.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Since the qualitative is incorporated into the design to explore the issue, a quasi-experimental employed with entrenched qualitative research design method of the action research (Creswell & Clark, 2007). Since there are several questions to be answered and multiple data sets would be needed to improve the application of the design, the embedded data is used because one data set is insufficient.

Population

The research population consists of student of science subject in primary level classes. This population chosen because some student enrolled during mid of the session and to see the impact of assessment strategies on the performance of student. The sample was used for this research consisted of students enrolled in grade 2 to 5 at primary school in Karachi.

Research Instrument

For this study, utilized pre-test and post-test and questionnaire for collection of information.

Data Collection and Analysis

- Data collections strategies include pre-test and post-test unit tests.
- Student's pre and post test results were tabulated and analyzed statistically, using t-test, statistical description and mean scores.
- Interpretive texts supplied after each table including quantitative data.
- To normalize whether there was a significant difference between the pre and post test results of control and treatment groups, a t-test would be employed.

DISCUSSION AND FINDINGS

Table 4.1 presents the pre- and post-test results for the descriptive statistics unit test. The treatment group's average was 27.14, whereas the control group's was 21.47, the students' performance on the pre-test was subpar. Given their prior, albeit limited, understanding of the subject, this is to be expected.

Table 1*Descriptive Statistics of Students' Pretest and Posttest on Unit Test Scores*

Variable	No. of student	Pre-test		Post-test	
		Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean	Standard Deviation
Treatment group	35	27.14	7.63	60.11	10.60
Control group	34	21.47	5.74	37.62	10.16

After the study session, it was noted that both students' academic performance of post test on unit test improved. Comparing the pre-test results for treatment group (Mean = 27.14, Standard Deviation = 7.63) and the results of post test (Mean = 60.11, Standard Deviation = 10.60) to those of the control group (Mean = 21.47, Standard Deviation = 5.74) and the results of post test (Mean = 37.62, Standard Deviation = 10.16), Table 3 demonstrates a significant rise in the students' averages on the unit test. The findings suggest that compared to the control group, a higher degree of prior knowledge of the unit under evaluation was demonstrated by 48 students in the treatment group.

To determine whether there was a significant difference between the mean scores of the pre test and Unit test and t-test was employed. The balancing sample t-test was used to assess how the intervention affected students' academic performance on a unit test (Table 4.2). Both the control group ($t(33) = -10.67, p < .0005$) and the treatment group ($t(34) = -21.73, p < .005$), showed statistically significant increases in test scores. The paired mean difference for the therapy group, however, varied significantly. The treatment group's unit test scores before and after the intervention differed significantly, according to the eta square statistic (.93), which suggested a big impact size.

Table 4.2*Compare means- Paired Samples Test between Pre-test and Post unit test*

Group	Mean	SD	t	sig
TG pre-test and post-test mean score	-32.97	9	-21073	00
CG pre-test and post-test mean score	-16.117	8.82	-10.67	00

The null hypothesis that evaluation procedures have no effect on student performance would not be accepted due to the aforementioned values. In other words, student performance is impacted by assessment strategies.

The outcome displayed a summary of the treatment group's descriptive data distribution. In the unit test, the bottom tail was longer and the median line was not uniformly distributed in the box. There was a positive skew to the right in the data distribution. The median line, which is greater than the pre-test median score but lower in the box, indicates a better performance.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the data analysis, it can be inferred that primary school children in grades nine through ten are enrolled. Numerous studies have demonstrated that using formative assessment techniques on a regular basis improves student performance and accomplishment on tests. Students that get formative and summative evaluation procedures may perform better, according to the data gathered for this study. The information gathered for this study contributes to the body of knowledge already available on how students' perceptions of the formative assessment techniques employed by teachers in the classroom can alter their affect. The evidence backs up the efforts of educators and school administrators to use assessments more to aid students' learning and to move away from a heavy reliance on student learning assessments.

- There is a connection between the kind of teaching strategy employed in the classroom and the improvement of students on the posttest. Compared to students in the control group, those exposed to the non-traditional manner demonstrated noticeably greater cognitive gain.
- Curriculum designers, teacher trainers, and legislators must keep motivating educators by offering assistance with ongoing, pertinent teaching training techniques. In elementary school, the class size should be lowered to 20–25 pupils in order to optimize student-teacher contact.
- Effective group work is difficult to complete in a single period; perhaps two periods would be more appropriate. This would guarantee that every group stays focused and has the opportunity to present their findings to the class.

References

- Abejehu, S.B. (2016). The practice of continuous assessment in primary schools: The case of Chagni, Ethiopia. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 7(13).
- Black, P., & William, D. (1998). Assessment and Classroom Learning. *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy, & Practice*, 5, 7-74. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0969595980050102>
- Broadfoot, (1979). *Assessment, Schools and Society*. London, Routledge.
- Brooks et al., (2021). Teachers activating learners: The effects of a student-centred feedback approach on writing achievement. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 105 (2021), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2021.103387>
- Charman et al., (1995). Personality and religious beliefs: A test of Flugel's Superego Projection Theory. *International Journal for the Psychology of Religion*, 5(2), 109-117 https://doi.org/10.1207/s15327582ijpr0502_5
- Christoforidou & Kyriakides, (2021). Developing teacher assessment skills: The impact of the dynamic approach to teacher professional development. *Studies in Educational Evaluation*, 70 (2021), Article 101051, 10.1016/j.stueduc.2021.101051
- Christoforidou et al., (2014). Searching for stages of teacher's skills in assessment. *Studies in Educational Evaluation*, 40 (2014), pp. 1-11.
- Creemers et al., (2013). A dynamic approach to school improvement: Main features and impact. *School Leadership & Management*, 33 (2) (2013), pp. 114-132, 10.1080/13632434.2013.773883
- Creswell, J. W., & Clark, V. L. P. (2007). *Designing and Conducting Mixed Methods Research*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Desimone, (2009). Improving impact studies of teachers' professional development: Toward better conceptualizations and measures. *Educational Researcher*, 38 (3) (2009).
- Eckstein, (1996). "Culture as a Foundation Concept for the Social Sciences," *Journal of Theoretical Politics*, 8(4), p-471-497.
- Francom & Gardner, (2014). What is task-centered learning? *Tech Trends*, 58 (5) (2014), pp. 27-35
- Gipps, (1994). *Towards a Theory of Educational Assessment*. London, Routledge.
- Harlen, W. (2007). *Assessment of Learning*. London: Sage Publications.
- Harris, L. R., & G. T. L. Brown (2018). *Using Self-Assessment to Improve Student Learning*. New York: Routledge.
- Heitink, Van der Kleij, Veldkamp, Schildkamp, & Kippers, (2016). A systematic review of prerequisites for implementing assessment for learning in classroom practice. *Educational Research Review*, 17 (2016), pp. 50-62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2015.12.002>
- Keeves, J.P. (1994). *Learning Science in a Changing World*. Cross-National Studies of Science Achievement: 1970 to 1984. IEA, The Hague.
- Kingston & Nash, (2011). Formative assessment: A meta-analysis and a call for research. *Educational Measurement: Issues and Practice*, 30 (4) (2011), pp. 28-37, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-3992.2011.00220.x>
- Kippers, Wolterinck, Schildkamp, Poortman, & Visscher, (2018). Teachers' views on the use of assessment for learning and data-based decision making in classroom practice. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 75, pp. 199-213 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2018.06.015>
- Myers, D. G. (1986). *Psychology*. Worth Publishers.
- Merrill, (2012). *First principles of instruction*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Prouty, J. D & George. E. S. (2003). *Continuous assessment: A practical guide for teachers*. American Institute for Research.
- Ramsden et.al., (1986). Effects of learning skills interventions on first year university students' learning. *Human Learning*, 5, 151-164.
- Webb, G.F. (1985). *Theory of Non-Linear Age Dependent Population Dynamics*. Marcel Dekker Inc., New York.
- Yan, Z. (2020). "Self-Assessment in the Process of Self-Regulated Learning and Its Relationship with Academic Achievement." *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education* 45:224–238. doi:10.1080/02602938.2019.1629390.
- Yan, Z., & D. Boud (2022). "Conceptualizing Assessment-as-Learning." In *Assessment as Learning: Maximizing Opportunities for Student Learning and Achievement*, edited by Z. Yan, and L. Yang, 11–24. New York: Routledge.